

RED CELL DISTRIBUTION WIDTH, AN INFLAMMATORY MARKER OF ACUTE ST SEGMENT ELEVATION MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION (STEMI) SEVERITY; ECHOCARDIOGRAPHIC ASSESSMENT

¹Azher Abbas Naser, ²Salam Naser Zangana, ^{3*}Iman Jabbar Kadhim, ⁴Falah Abdulhasan Deli and ⁵Wijdan Rajh Hamza Al-Kraity

¹M.B. Ch.B. MSc. (Path), MSc. (Res), MSc. (Echo) Teacher, University of Warith Anbyaa, College of Medicine, Internal Medicine.

²M.B. Ch.B. DM, FICS, CABMS, FRCP (Glasg), FRCP (Edin); Professor Hawller University/ College of Medicine, Internal Medicine.

³M.B. Ch.B., DCM, MSC Microbiology; Assistant Professor, University of Kufa, Faculty of Medicine, Community Medicine.

⁴M.B. Ch.B. FICMS, Professor, University of Warith Anbyaa, College of Medicine, Internal Medicine.

⁵MB Ch.B. Ph.D. Med Phys., Assistant Professor, University of Kufa, Faculty of Medicine, Medical Physiology.

Article Received date: 14 November 2024

Article Revised date: 04 December 2024

Article Accepted date: 24 December 2024

*Corresponding Author: Iman Jabbar Kadhim

M.B. Ch.B., DCM, MSC Microbiology; Assistant Professor, University of Kufa, Faculty of Medicine, Community Medicine. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17129208>

ABSTRACT

Background: Increasing value of Red cell distribution width (RDW) is documented to be linked to worse clinical outcomes so that it can be considered as a prognostic indicator in states like acute myocardial infarction coupled with other inflammatory markers taking in consideration its easy availability. **Aim of the study:** This study aimed to assess the relationship of RDW and echocardiographic parameters especially systolic and diastolic dysfunction in patients with ST-elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI). **Patients and methods:** In this study 60 {38 (63%) were males and 22 (37%) females} consecutive patients who had acute ST elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) at Rozhalat hospital, Erbil, Iraq were included, RDW was obtained during the event of STEMI and the levels obtained were analyzed according to measures of systolic and diastolic dysfunction calculated by transthoracic echocardiographic study. **Results:** RDW was found to be increasing in patients with impaired systolic and diastolic functions (ejection fraction of the left ventricle <50%, diastolic filling wave (E/A)<1, peak early transmitral velocity over early diastolic annular velocity [E/E'] >10, and more obviously with combined E/A < 1 and E/E' > 10 (P <0.01). The best cut off value of RDW was 13% with sensitivity (75.9%) and specificity (61.3%) and this is obtained applying ROC curve analysis according to echocardiography ejection fraction 50%. **Conclusion:** Elevated RDW can be considered as a new biomarker of poor outcome in patients acute STEMI patients as it is associated with diastolic as well as and to a lesser extent systolic dysfunction in patients with STEMI even after adjustment of several confounding factors.

INTRODUCTION

Globally, ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) continues to be an utmost important etiology of cardiac mortality and morbidity and so it is crucial to specify the patients with increased risk who is in need for more intensive care and follow-up.^[1,2] Echocardiogram is one of the important investigations for evaluating patients after acute ischemic events, the access to echocardiography is quite easy at city and peripheral hospitals and medical centers but there are a lot of obstacles including being time consuming and operator dependent procedure and this possibly mandates a need of easily interpretable and low cost marker by which we

can predict the disturbance of left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) at early assessment of patient with acute myocardial infarction.^[3]

Recently many studies showed an association between adverse outcome of cardiovascular diseases and elevated RDW and so it can be considered as a respectful parameter for both diagnostic application and prediction for outcome in various settings of cardiovascular issues.^[3,4]

Felker et al. (2007) study was one of the earliest studies to assess the role of RDW in diseases of cardiovascular

system, where by a prognostic value of RDW in patients with heart failure (HF) was observed.^[4] The same result was shown in states other than heart failure, as in acute coronary syndromes.^[5,6,7,8] further more many researches documented a relation of RDW with the echocardiographic features of systolic as well as diastolic dysfunction in many cardiovascular conditions.^[9,10,11,12]

AIM OF THE STUDY

This study aimed to assess the relationship of RDW and echocardiographic parameters especially systolic and diastolic dysfunction in patients with ST-elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) ascertaining its predictive values taking in consideration these and more other echocardiographic parameters.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

This is a single-center, cross sectional observational study done at Department of Emergency Medicine, Rozhalat hospital, Erbil, Iraq from June 15th, 2022 to June 14th, 2024. 60 (patients with acute myocardial infarction were assessed, all these patients had no other important cardiac or respiratory illness and patients with a history of chronic hematological and inflammatory conditions were excluded from the study.

Echocardiography: Echocardiography through transthoracic access was done and all measurements were taken by one expert echocardiographer and using the same equipment. LVEF along with wall motion abnormalities and valvular pathologies were recorded for each patient.

The measurements were recorded from 3 consecutive cycles, and the mean values were considered for the study. The test was performed at the first week after the STEMI. The echocardiography was performed by the echocardiography machine (Vivid E9, GE Healthcare, Horten, Norway) with a 1.5—4 MHz sector transducer probe.

The following parameters were recorded; Fractional shortening (FS %): (LV diameter at end of diastole - LV diameter at end of systole)/LV diameter at end diastole (25%—43%: male, 27-45%: female). Left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF %) applying the Modified Simpson method (52%—72%: male, 54-74%: female).^[13]

LV end-systolic diameter and LV end-diastolic diameter obtained by M-mode

End-diastolic interventricular septal thickness.

End-diastolic LV posterior wall thickness.

LV diastolic filling patterns were assessed by Doppler examination of the inflow pulsed wave of mitral valve, best obtained through the view of apical 4-chamber.^[14]

The diastolic measures were taken by three beats and defined as. E-wave: early maximal flow velocity transmitral.

A-wave: peak velocity at late diastole during atrial contraction

E/A ratio: ratio between (E) and (A).

According to age group Left ventricular diastolic dysfunction was documented as E/A is <1.3 (at ages 45-49 years), <1.2 (at ages 50-59 years), <1.0 (at ages 60-69 years), and <0.8 (70 years and older).^[15]

Statistical analysis

IBM Statistical Package of Social Science (SPSS) Statistics. Independent sample t-test, Chi-squared test (χ^2) were applied as indicated. Numerical variables optimal cut-off values was analysed according to Receiver operating characteristic (ROC). Logistic regression test was applied for Multivariate analyses to document the presence of systolic and diastolic dysfunction. ($p \leq 0.05$) was considered a statistically significant. Ethical approval was obtained from ethical committee of scientific researches of the Iraqi board of internal medicine.

RESULTS

In this study 60 patients (38 (63%) males and 22 (37%) females) were included, the patients' echocardiographic features are shown in Table 1. The mean left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) of studied participants was 52.5 ± 6.9 %; 23 (38.3%) of them had LVEF of less than 50%. The mean peak velocity of the early diastolic filling wave (E) of the patients was 0.64 ± 0.19 and the mean peak velocity of the late diastolic filling wave (A) was 0.71 ± 0.12 . While 41 (68.3%) patients had peak velocity flow in early diastole to peak velocity flow in late diastole (E/A) of less than 1, the mean E/A ratio of the participants was 0.9 ± 0.25 . The mean early transmitral velocity and early diastolic annular velocity ratio (E/E') of the participants was 9.5 ± 2 , and 39 (65%) of them had E/E' ratio of more than 10. The combination of E/A <1 and E/E' >10 was detected in 28 (46.7%) patients. According to these results, a significant association between low LVEF (<50%) and high RDW levels ($p < 0.006$) was observed. The mean A of the high RDW group was higher than the mean A of the next group ($p < 0.001$). A highly significant association was observed between **E/A ratio** <1 and high RDW levels ($p < 0.001$). There was a dramatically significant association between patients with E/E' >10 and high RDW levels ($p < 0.001$). The mean E/E' of high RDW group was higher compared to mean E/E' of low RDW group ($p < 0.001$). Significantly higher RDW readings were documented in patients with E/E' >10. A highly significant association was observed between patients with E/A <1 and E/E' >10 and high RDW levels ($p < 0.001$). RDW values detected in patients with E/A < 1 combined with E/E' > 10 were shown to be higher.

There was no important differences between both groups regarding mean LVEF, LVEDD, LVESD, E value, and tricuspid annular plane systolic excursion TAPSE.

Table 1: Echocardiographic characteristics of the two groups.

Variables	All patients N=60	Patient with low RDW N=32	Patients with high RDW N=28	P value
LVEF mean±SD	52.5±6.9 %	54.8±7.5	51.3±10.3	0.073** ^{NS}
LVEF<50%	23(38.3)	9(28.1)	14(50.0)	0.006
LVEDD mean±SD	51±4.3	51.9±2.4	50.9±1.9	0.09** ^{NS}
LVESD mean±SD	36.5±4.4	37.3±2.4	37.6±2.3	0.6** ^{NS}
E mean±SD	0.64±0.19	0.64±0.1	0.63±0.2	0.8** ^{NS}
A mean±SD	0.71±0.12	0.63±0.09	0.78±0.09	<0.001 ** ^S
E/A mean±SD	0.9±0.25	1.1±0.2	0.7±0.17	<0.001 ** ^S
E/A<1	41(68.3)	14(43.8)	27(96.4)	<0.001 * ^S
E/E' mean±SD	9.5±2	7.9±0.8	11.1±1.5	<0.001 ** ^S
E/E' >10	39(65)	19(59.3)	21(75.4)	<0.001 * ^S
TAPSE mean±SD	19.5±1.13	19.4±1	19.6±1.2	0.4** ^{NS}
Combination of E/A<1 and E/E'>10	28(46.7)	8(25)	20(71.4)	<0.001

Using bivariate correlations analysis, RDW values have negative correlation with LVEF (P<0.01, Rho= - 1.0) and E/A (P<0.01, Rho=-0.99), and a positively significant association with E/E' (P=0.01, Rho= 1.0), as shown in Figure 1 (A-C). A positive association between RDW and A (P<0.001, Rho=0.36) was observed (D).

A

B

C

Figure 1: Correlation of values of RDW with LVEF, E/A ratio and E/E ratio. (A) RDW values were correlated negatively with LVEF, (B) Correlated negatively with E/A ratio,(C) Correlated positively with E/E'.(D) Positive correlation with A.

Using receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis, we ascertained practical cutoff points of RDW to differentiate patients having systolic/diastolic dysfunction from others (Fig2. A–D).

Cutoff RDW values of 13% were applied to ascertain patients with **LVEF < 50%** (AUC 0.7, P<007) with acceptable validity results (a sensitivity of 76%, a specificity of 61%, a positive predictive value (PPV) of 60%; and a negative predictive value (NPV) of 79% and accuracy 70%), figure 2.

The acceptable cut off points and the corresponding validity values for RDW values in prediction of E/A<1(AUC 0.73, P<.001) were shown in table 2 and figure 2. RDW values of 14 % were perfect to document patients with **E/A < 1** with a sensitivity of 63.4%; a specificity of 94.7%; a positive predictive value (PPV) of 67%; and a negative predictive value (NPV) of 93% and accuracy 75%.

The acceptable cut off points and the corresponding validity values for RDW level in prediction of **E/E'>10**(AUC 0.88, P<.001) was shown in table 2 and figure 2, values of 14 had acceptable validity results (94.7% sensitivity, 78% specificity, 72.8%PPV, 93% NPV and accuracy 85%) for the prediction of E/E'>10.

RDW values of 14% were regarded to ascertain patients featuring **both E/A < 1 and E/E' > 10** (AUC 0.88, P<.001) with a sensitivity of 94.7%; a specificity of 78%; a positive predictive value (PPV) of 72.8%; and a negative predictive value (NPV) of 93% and accuracy 85%.

The acceptable cutoff point for predicting diastolic heart failure (DHF) was 14%. (Table 2).

Diagonal segments are produced by ties.

Diagonal segments are produced by ties.

A) ROC for RDW prediction of E/A<1 (AUC=0.73).

B) ROC for RDW prediction of EFLV<50% (AUC=0.7).

C) ROC for RDW prediction of E/E' > 10 (AUC=0.88). D) ROC for RDW prediction of E/A < 1 and E/E' > 10 (AUC=0.88).

Figure 2: Receiver operating characteristic curve analysis for RDW in assessing patients with (A) E/A < 1 (B) EFLV < 50%, (C) E/E' > 10, and (D) Combined E/A < 1 and E/E' > 10.

Table 2: ROC coordinates for prediction of low EFLV < 50%, E/A < 1, E/E' > 10 and combined E/A < 1 and E/E' > 10 by RDW.

Cutoff point low EFLV < 50%	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV	Accuracy
12%	93.1%	28.6%	45.4%	83.2%	58%
13%	75.9%	61.3%	60.2%	78.5%	70%
14%	65.5%	74.2%	72.8%	63%	69%
Cutoff point E/A < 1	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV	Accuracy
12	82.9%	21.1%	31.8%	73.4%	48%
13	68.3%	68.4%	66.7%	68.5%	67%
14	63.4%	94.7%	66.7%	93%	75%
Cutoff point E/E' > 10	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV	Accuracy
12	100%	26.8%	21.2%	93.4%	38%
13	100%	36.8%	31.2%	94.4%	48%
14	94.7%	78%	72.8%	93%	85%
Cutoff point E/A < 1 and E/E' > 10	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV	Accuracy
12	100%	27.2%	25.7%	98.0%	43%
13	100%	46.9%	41.1%	96.2%	57.6%
14	94.7%	78%	72.8%	93%	85%

DISCUSSION

RDW was approved to be the predictor of all cause mortalities in two large studies.^[16,17] RDW was concluded to be a good indicator for expecting worse outcome in heart failure patients.^[18,19] RDW predicts independently one-year mortality following acute heart failure attacks regardless of anemia status,^[20,21] other studies documented that increasing RDW levels are associated significantly with a bad results in patients of

acute myocardial infarction and patients undergoing percutaneous coronary intervention^[3,22,23]

Bujak et al. assessed the importance of RDW in CAD as a prognostic indicator, predicting that such a rule primarily results from the effect of oxidative stress of inflammation and deficiency of vitamin D3 and iron on erythropoiesis in bone marrow^[24], this is supported by multiple studies documenting that inflammatory factors, as interleukin 6, WBC count, fibrinogen level and C-

reactive protein (CRP) affects homeostasis of erythrocyte and leading possibly to increased values of RDW by decreasing red blood cell survival through impairment of iron manipulation, and affecting the release or the effect of erythropoietin.^[25,26]

In this work, increasing RDW predicts both systolic and diastolic dysfunction after STEMI, RDW correlated with diastolic more precisely than systolic dysfunction; and 14% values of RDW may be valuable for excluding a combined $E/A < 1$ and $E/E' > 10$ situation due to a significant good negative predictive value. RDW, In multivariate analyses constantly shown to be precisely associated with values of both systolic and diastolic dysfunction ($EF < 50\%$, $E/A < 1$, $E/E' > 10$) as a single existence or combined in a multiple logistic regression models after adjustment of several confounders as age, gender, TIMI score, and consistent with this study, Karakas found that raised RDW at admission was associated with systolic dysfunction after STEMI^[9] and this is consistent with our results. Van Kimmenade *et al.*^[7] also featured that the increment of RDW in patients with acute cardiac failure was independent of nutritional status, inflammation or history of transfusion. Additionally, Allen *et al.* in a recent research found that raised RDW may point to inflammatory stress and impairment of iron mobilization in heart failure patients.^[28]

In the management of coronary disease the analysis of diastolic dysfunction as well as systolic one also has a rule in both diagnosis and prognosis.^[29,30] Inconsistence with many recent studies, subclinical diastolic dysfunction is expected in a good percent of patients^[12], according to Kitzman *et al.*^[31] neurohormonal changes resembling those documented in systolic heart failure occur in diastolic one.

The positive relation between increased RDW and E/E' , in this study indicates that rise in left ventricular filling pressure (LVFP) may be the initiative for the increase in RDW in patients with DHF. Oh *et al.*^[32] documented a relation between RDW elevation and E/E' in patients with acute cardiac failure, and the most appropriate cutoff value of RDW for predicting $E/E' > 15$ is suggested to be 13.45%.

An important finding in this study was that increasing RDW may reflect exaggerated myocardial injury in patients with either STEMI or ACS, and it can regarded as a marker of occurrence of events of coronary heart disease in different cardiovascular conditions and of all-cause mortality.^[33,34] Cavusoglu *et al.*, observed that the RDW was also documented to be a relevant factor that is independent of all-cause mortality in patients sustained ACS^[22], this is documented in this study where by Patients with RDW > 13.9 had significantly higher TIMI risk scores and ASCVD.

CONCLUSIONS

Elevated RDW can be considered as a new marker of poor outcome in patients acute STEMI as it associated with diastolic as well as and to a lesser extent systolic dysfunction in patients with STEMI even after adjustment of several confounding factors.

REFERENCES

1. Fox KA, Cokkinos DV, Deckers J, *et al.* The ENACT study: apan-European survey of acute coronary syndromes. *Eur Heart J.*, 2000; 21: 1440-9
2. Fox KA, Goodman SG, Anderson FA Jr, *et al.*, GRACE Investigators. From guidelines to clinical practice: the impact of hospital and geographical characteristics on temporal trends in the management of acute coronary syndromes. The Global Registry of Acute Coronary Events (GRACE). *Eur Heart J.*, 2003; 24: 1414-24.
3. Isik T, Ayhan E, Kurt M, Tanboga IH, Kaya A, Aksakal E. Is Red Cell Distribution Width a Marker for the presence and Poor Prognosis of Cardiovascular Disease? *EAJM.*, 2012; 44(3): 169-71.
4. Felker GM, Allen LA, Pocock SJ, Shaw LK, McMurray JJ, Pfeffer MA. Red cell distribution width as a novel prognostic maker in heart failure J. *Am Coll Cardiol*, 2007; 50(1): 40-7.
5. Van Kimmenade RR, Mohammed AA, Uthamalingam S, *et al.* Red blood cell distribution width and 1-year mortality in acute heart failure. *Eur J Heart Fail*, 2010; 12: 129–36.
6. Osadnik T, Strzelczyk J, Hawranek M, *et al.* Red cell distribution width is associated with long-term prognosis in patients with stable coronary artery disease. *BMC Cardiovasc Disord.*, 2013; 13: 113.
7. Tenekecioglu E, Yilmaz M, Yontar OC, *et al.* Red blood cell distribution width is associated with myocardial injury in non-ST-elevation acute coronary syndrome. *Clinics*, 2015; 70: 18–23.
8. Lucijanic M, Pejisa V, Jaksic O, *et al.* The degree of anisocytosis predicts survival in patients with primary myelofibrosis. *Acta Haematol*, 2016; 136: 98–100.
9. Karakas MS, Korucuk N, Tosun V, *et al.* Red cell distribution width and neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio predict left ventricular dysfunction in acute anterior ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction. *J Saudi Heart Assoc.*, 2016; 28: 152–8.
10. Gromadzinski L, Januszko-Giergielewicz B, Pruszczyk P. Red cell distribution width is an independent factor for left ventricular diastolic dysfunction in patients with chronic kidney disease. *Clin Exp Nephrol*, 2015; 19: 616–25.
11. Alattar FT, Imran NB, Patel P, *et al.* Red cell distribution width (RDW) correlates with markers of diastolic dysfunction in patients with impaired left ventricular systolic function. *Int J Cardiol Heart Vasc.*, 2016; 10: 13–6.
12. Senthong V, Hudec T, Neale S, *et al.* Relation of red cell distribution width to left ventricular end-

- diastolic pressure and mortality in patients with and without heart failure. *Am J Cardiol.*, 2017; 119: 1421–7.
13. Teichholz LE, Kreulen T, Herman MV, Gorlin R. Problems in echocardiographic volume determinations: echocardiographic-angiographic correlations in the presence of absence of asynergy. *Am J Cardiol*, 1976; 37: 7-11.
 14. Kaul S, Tei C, Hopkins JM, Shah PM. Assessment of right ventricular function using two-dimensional echocardiography. *Am Heart J.*, 1984; 107: 526-31.
 15. Braunwald's Heart Disease. 8th Edition. By Libby P, Bonow RO, Zipes DP, Mann DL. Philadelphia: Saunders, 2018; 251.
 16. Patel KV, Ferrucci L, Ershler WB, Longo DL, Guralnik JM. Red blood cell distribution width and the risk of death in middle-aged and older adults. *Arch Intern Med.*, 2009; 169: 515-23.
 17. Perlstein TS, Weuve J, Pfeffer MA, Beckman JA. Red blood cell distribution width and mortality risk in a community-based prospective cohort. *Arch Intern Med.*, 2009; 169: 588-94.
 18. Al-Najjar Y, Goode KM, Zhang J, Cleland JG, Clark AL. Red cell distribution width: an inexpensive and powerful prognostic marker in heart failure. *Eur J Heart Fail*, 2009; 11: 1155-62.
 19. Forhe'cz Z, Gombos T, Borgulya G, Pozsonyi Z, Proha'szka Z, Ja'noskuti L. Red cell distribution width in heart failure: prediction of clinical events and relationship with markers of ineffective erythropoiesis, inflammation, renal function, and nutritional state. *Am Heart J.*, 2009; 158: 659-66.
 20. Van Kimmenade RR, Mohammed AA, Uthamalingam S, van der Meer P, Felker GM, Januzzi Jr JL. Red blood cell distribution width and 1-year mortality in acute heart failure. *Eur J Heart Fail*, 2010; 12: 129-36.
 21. Pascual-Figal DA, Bonaque JC, Redondo B, Caro C, Manzano-Fernandez S, Sa'nchez-Mas J, and et al. Red blood cell distribution width predicts long-term outcome regardless of anaemia status in acute heart failure patients. *Eur J Heart Fail*, 2009; 11: 840-6.
 22. Cavusoglu E, Chopra V, Gupta A, Battala VR, Poludasu S, Eng C, et al. Relation between red blood cell distribution width (RDW) and all-cause mortality at two years in an unselected population referred for coronary angiography. *Int J Cardiol*, 2010; 141: 141-6.
 23. Poludasu S, Marmur JD, Weedon J, Khan W, Cavusoglu E. Red cell distribution width (RDW) as a predictor of long-term mortality in patients undergoing percutaneous coronary intervention. *Thromb Haemost*, 2009; 102: 581-7.
 24. Bujak K, Wasilewski J, Osadnik T, Jonczyk S, Kołodziejaska A, Gierlotka M, Gąsior M. The prognostic role of red blood cell distribution width in coronary artery disease: a review of the pathophysiology. *Dis Markers*, 2015; 2015: 824624.
 25. Rechavi G, Rivella S. Regulation of iron absorption in hemoglobinopathies. *Curr Mol Med.*, 2008; 8(7): 646–62.
 26. Schieffer B, Schieffer E, Hilfiker-Kleiner D, Hilfiker A, Kovanen PT, Kaartinen M, Nussberger J, Harringer W, Drexler H. Expression of angiotensin II and interleukin 6 in human coronary atherosclerotic plaques: potential implications for inflammation and plaque instability. *Circulation*, 2000; 101(12): 1372–8.
 27. Akpek M, Kaya MG, Uyarel H, et al: The association of serum uric acid levels on coronary flow in patients with STEMI undergoing primary PCI. *Atherosclerosis*, 2011; 219: 334–341.
 28. Allen LA, Felker GM, Mehra MR, Chiong JR, Dunlap SH, Ghali JK, et al. Validation and potential mechanisms of red cell distribution width as a prognostic marker in heart failure. *J Card Fail*, 2010; 16: 230-8.
 29. Ohara T, Little WC. Evolving focus on diastolic dysfunction in patients with coronary artery disease. *Curr Opin Cardiol.*, 2010; 25: 613–21.
 30. Du LJ, Dong PS, Jia JJ, et al. Association between left ventricular end diastolic pressure and coronary artery disease as well as its extent and severity. *Int J Clin Exp Med.*, 2015; 8: 18673–80.
 31. Kitzman DW, Little WC, Brubaker PH, Anderson RT, Hundley WG, Marburger CT, et al. Pathophysiological characterization of isolated diastolic heart failure in comparison to systolic heart failure. *JAMA.*, 2002; 288: 2144-50.
 32. Oh J, Kang SM, Hong N, Choi JW, Lee SH, Park S, et al. Relation between red cell distribution width with echocardiographic parameters in patients with acute heart failure. *J Card Fail*, 2009; 15: 517-22.
 33. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), National Center for Health Statistics. National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey data. Available at: www.cdc.gov/nchs/nhanes.htm. Accessed on March 15, 2010.
 34. Helfand M, Buckley DI, Freeman M, Fu R, Rogers K, Fleming C, et al. Emerging risk factors for coronary heart disease: a summary of systematic reviews conducted for the U.S. Preventive Services Task Force. *Ann Intern Med.*, 2009; 151(7): 496-507.